

LIQUID RENEWABLE ENERGY CARRIERS FROM
CAPTURED CARBON EMISSIONS

DELIVERABLE D1.5

Project Management Plan (First Update)

PROJECT NO:
101118265

PROJECT ACRONYM:
CAPTUS

PROJECT TITLE:
Demonstrating energy intensive industry-
integrated solutions to produce liquid renewable
energy carriers from CAPTURED carbon emissionS

CALL/TOPIC:
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Associated Task	T1.2
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DISSEMINATION LEVEL

PU	Public – fully open	X
SEN	Sensitive – limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement	

CHANGE CONTROL

DOCUMENT HISTORY

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1.0	16/09/24	DRAFT	Francisco Javier Real Salas	CIRCE
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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The deliverable D1.5 is an update of the previous Project Management Plan of the project (D1.3). It includes a detailed Project Management Plan with a Gantt chart per work package and a Work Breakdown Structure (WBS). The deliverable provides an overview of the objectives of the CAPTUS Project, delineates the project's work structure, and elaborates on the roles of all participants involved. Additionally, it illustrates the interactions between various work packages and incorporates checkpoints to monitor progress and meet specific objectives and expectations.

Being a dynamic document, this deliverable will undergo two other updates during the course of the project (M34 and M48) to ensure it remains relevant and up to date.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

ACRONYM	DESCRIPTION
C&D	Communication and Dissemination
CA	Consortium Agreement
CCUS	Carbon capture utilisation and storage
COO	Coordinator
CUU	Capture, Utilization, and Upcycling
CSAR	Continuous Swing Adsorption Reactor
D1	Demonstrator 1 EEI (Steel) Belgium
D2	Demonstrator 2 EEI (Chemical) Portugal
D3	Demonstrator 1 EEI (Cement) Spain
DLV/dlv	Deliverable
DMP	Data management Plan
DoA	Description of Action (annex I of the Grant Agreement)
DSO	Distribution System Operators
DSP	Downstream Processing
EC	European Commission
EEI	energy intensive industries
ERCO2	CO2 electrocatalytic reduction
ESS	Energy Storage Systems
GA	Grant Agreement
GCPV	Grupo Cementos Portland Valderrivas
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HTL	Hydrothermal liquefaction
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
KPI	Key Project Indicator
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LCC	Life Cycle Costs
LCSA	Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment

MS	Milestone
P2P	Peer-to-peer
PBR	photobioreactor
PC	Project Coordinator
PERT	Program Evaluation and Review Technique
PGEP	Project Gender Equality Plan
PMP	Project Management Plan
PSA	Pressure Swing Adsorption
PO	Project Officer
PV	Photovoltaics
R&D	research and development
RECs	renewable energy carriers
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation
s-LCA	Social Life Cycle Assessment
SME	Small and medium enterprise
TAG	Triacylglycerol
TL	Task Leader
ToC	Table of Contents
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
TP	Technical Partners
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

1 INTRODUCTION

The primary purpose of this initial version of the CAPTUS Project Management Plan (referred to as PMP hereafter) is to foster alignment among all partners towards common goals. It achieves this by meticulously outlining the various work packages, their interdependencies, and task relationships.

To minimize misunderstandings, conflicts, and resource misuse, the PMP establishes the main and specific objectives of the project, a timeline for activities, and checkpoints for monitoring work progress.

This deliverable D1.5 is an update of deliverable 1.3, the Project Management Plan, which presents an overview of the CAPTUS Project's objectives, work structure breakdown, participant details, and their respective roles. It also illustrates the interactions between work packages and incorporates progress checkpoints to ensure specific objectives and expectations are met.

As the project advances, the PMP evolves to accurately reflect the current state of consortium agreements concerning time schedules for tasks and subtasks, responsible partners, and task dependencies on other activities and outcomes. The PMP is planned to undergo another additional update in M34, as stipulated in Annex I of the Grant Agreement N° 101118265.

This deliverable has been developed following the standard practices and approaches used by CIRCE in project coordination. The coordinator has established methodologies and recognized guidelines in project management, which have been used as a reference for structuring and executing this project with the purpose of promoting efficient management.

The team responsible for this deliverable has applied their knowledge and experience to implement CIRCE's standard practices appropriately and consistently with the specific needs and characteristics of this project.

2 TEAM COMPOSITION AND ROLES PER ENTITY

This section introduces the members per entity and their role and participation within the CAPTUS Project.

Table 1: CAPTUS Team participants and role

ENTITY	PARTNERS	ROLE IN THE PROJECT
CIRCE	Francisco Javier Real Salas Monique Bernardes Jaime Guerrero Christian Aragón Miguel Cámara David Miguel Rivas Romina Inés Lobera Noemi Galan Mikel Refoyo Eduardo Martinez Maria Santiago Gregorio Fernandez Lucía Baldoni Gonzalez Alberto Collado Ortega Alvaro Muñoz Martin	As Project Coordinator, CIRCE will ensure the correct execution of the project in terms of time, quality and costs (WP1). CIRCE is the main responsible optimisation of the HTL process in D2 (T4.3), simulation, modelling and optimization of CAPTUS technologies (T2.5 and T4.4), renewable energy integration and management (T6.2 and T6.3)
SINTEF	Henri Cloete Kurian Vachaparambil Canberk Ozan Lucas Braakhuis Bente Flataunet Silje Engan Stein Oddvar Søgård	Norwegian research organisation in charge of CO ₂ capture in D3 (T5.1)
UNICAN	Jose Angel Irabien Gullias Cristina Bolado Garcia Guillermo Diaz Sainz Aitor Marcos Lucía Gómez Coma Marta Rumayor Villamil Cristina González Fernández	Spanish University will be D3 demo leader, technology developer of electrochemical conversion stage (ERCO ₂) (T5.2, T5.3)
CSIC	Jorge Barriuso Maicas José Luis Garcia Lopez	Spanish research organisation will be the developer and provider of improved yeast

		strains in D1 for liquid fermentation processes (T3.2)
UNIGE	Stefano Barberis Daria Bellotti Chiara Monacchini	Italian University will lead the thermo-economic assessment (T6.5), digital agenda and social acceptance assessment (T8.3).
SIG	Francisco Javier Casado Hebrard Anthony Salingre Maren Hafner	The German innovation management organization is at the forefront of leading and conducting activities related to C&D in T8.1 and T8.2. Furthermore, they will actively seek and foster synergies with other relevant projects, (T8.5).
CERTH	Angelos Lappas Eleni Heracleous Stamatia Karakoulia Flora Papadopoulou	CERTH Greek research organization leads the characterization and upgrading studies of the obtained RECs (T6.1)
BBEPP	Lena Decuyper Koen Quataert Stefano Rebecchi Pedro Acuna Lopez Karel De Winter Esthle Goure Eliot Schrder	BBEPP is a SME company that will be D1 demo leader, technology developer (gas and liquid fermentation) (T.3.1, T3.3), scale-up and real demonstration of coupled fermentation process in D1 (T3.5).
NOVIS	Thomas Helle Christopher Oechner	NOVIS is a SME company that will be responsible for CO ₂ capture and conditioning of flue gas from the chemical plant in D2 (T4.1)
APRIA	Esther Santos Sophie Mary Schrder Barraza	ARPIA is a SME company that will leads engineering, scale-up and installation of CCU solutions in D3 (T5.4)
DRAXIS	Aida Anthouli Ioanna Pavlou Katerina Valta Giorgos Lanaras Sotiris Kottaridis Matina (Stamatia) Antonakoudi	DRAXIS is a SME company that will be responsible for LCA, s-LCA, LCC of CAPTUS REC value chains (T6.4)
A4F	Sara Badenes	A4F is a SME company that will be D2

	Bruno Sommer Ferreira Luís Costa Denise Costa Eduardo Rebelo	demo leader; technology developer of microalgae cultivation system, engineering and installation of PBRs (T4.2).
GF	Felipe Ferrari Thomas Groot Marilena Demetriou	GF is a company on charge of the IPR review and exploitation strategy (T7.2) also participating in the quality assessment of the produced RECs (T6.1)
RINA-C	Laura Bertolacci Susanna Penko Luca Ricci Marco ARIAGNO Francesca Parodi Alessio Pacchiana	RINA-C is a SME company that will be responsible for the Baseline assessment (T2.1, T2.2), guidelines and recommendations (T7.1), and business models (T7.4)
ARC	Eric Deconinck Yves De Veusser Wim Van der Stricht Marian Flores Granobles	ARC is a EII from the steel sector providing a real industrial environment in D1 (T3.4) to test its viability as innovative, sustainable flexibility assets.
HCH	Pedro Rodrigues Eduardo Rebelo Bruno Pires Arlindo Carvalho	HCH is a SME company EII from the chemical sector providing a real industrial environment in D2 (T4.5)
GCPV	Beatriz Malagon Picon Jose Calvo De La Fuente Jesus Bernando Pareja Cebrian	EII from the cement sector providing a real industrial environment in D3 (T5.5)
EEIP	Claire Chretien Jürgen Ritzek Dusan Jakovljevic Irene Paoletti	EEIP is a SME company that will lead the assessment of non-technical barriers for the valorisation of the RECs (T2.3), market readiness of CAPTUS technologies (T7.3), stakeholder engagement and EU networking (T8.4).
FE	Felipe Ferrari Thomas Groot Marilena Demetriou	FE is a company on charge of the IPR review and exploitation strategy (T7.2) also participating in the quality assessment of the produced RECs (T6.1)

As depicted in table 1, the CAPTUS project is set to be executed by a diverse and well-balanced

consortium consisting of 18 partners from 8 European countries. This consortium brings together expertise from various fields, ensuring a multidisciplinary approach to the project.

Figure 1: Map of CAPTUS consortium

3 WORK BREAKDOWN STRUCTURE

CAPTUS has a duration of 48 months and is divided into 8 different WPs. The first package is aimed to management and coordination of the project. The WP2 focuses on characterizing data, barriers, resources, and requirements to establish a baseline for CAPTUS solution development in subsequent technical WPs. It also defines pre- and post-implementation KPIs to set achievable targets for successful demo-site deployment.

WP3, WP4, and WP5 will concurrently develop and demonstrate CAPTUS technologies at three chosen demo-sites. The process in each WP involves designing, developing, and optimizing CUU and conversion technologies, followed by engineering, upscaling, and implementation of the optimized systems at respective industrial facilities. The final stage entails real demonstrations of CAPTUS solutions, achieving the required TRL (TRL 7).

WP6 will conduct impact assessments encompassing social, technical, and cost-benefit analyses to assess the feasibility and cost-efficiency of CAPTUS solutions. The quality evaluations and upgrading studies of the obtained liquid RECs will validate their suitability for utilization in the energy sector. Additionally, the integration of existing renewable sources will be thoroughly analysed and optimised to minimize renewable electricity curtailment, enhance overall efficiency, and promote synergy with carbon emissions reduction efforts.

In WP7, the findings from the demonstration activities will be utilized to develop exploitation and replication strategies. The regulatory and standardization landscape will be assessed, and a conducive framework will be created to foster the widespread adoption of CAPTUS solutions, aligned with profitable business models. This stage aims to facilitate the integration of CAPTUS technologies into various industries and markets.

Throughout the methodology phases, all partners will actively engage in communication and dissemination activities in WP8, aiming to reach a wide audience and maximize their involvement.

CAPTUS' Gantt chart is presented below and will be updated through the project's life cycle.

3.1 WP1: MANAGEMENT AND COORDINATION (M1-M48)

The **main objective** of this work package is to develop an effective and comprehensive administrative, financial, technical and legal management to ensure the successful execution of the project.

As for its **specific objectives**, this WP will:

1. To ensure the achievement of all project objectives in terms of time, quality and costs.
2. To set the appropriate coordination and management tools, methods and decision-making processes.
3. To perform smooth and effective management of the consortium, guaranteeing joint understanding among the project partners and ensuring the right functioning of the established governing bodies
4. To carry out periodic communication and high-quality technical and financial reporting of the project to EC.
5. To work together during the whole research and innovation process with the main societal actors.
6. To ensure the GDPR when treating with data external/internal to the project.
7. To ensure proactive inclusion and participation, also in online and hybrid events.

This WP is comprised of the following **deliverables**, all of them with CIRCE as lead beneficiary:

- D1.1: Project Handbook (M3). Related to Tasks 1.1,1.3,1.5: This document establishes the governance structure, communication methods, and reporting frequency to task and WP leaders, the Project Coordinator, and the European Commission. It also encompasses the Quality Plan, PGEP, Ethics Plan, and Collaborative Space Guide to ensure effective project management and adherence to ethical and quality standards.
- D1.2: Data Management Plan (M6). Related to Task 1.3. DMP will set the procedures for data sharing, communication and dissemination of the project. including:
 - Data set reference and name.
 - Data set descriptions,
 - Standards and metadata,
 - Data sharing,
 - Archiving
 - The 'ethics requirements' that the project must comply with
- D1.3: Project Management Plan (M2). Related to task 1.2. This deliverable includes a schedule per task, responsible partner related subtasks, related deliverables and dependencies on other tasks.
- D1.4: RRI: First report (M12). Related to task 1.4. Summary of RRI practices that will be used during the CAPTUS Project.
- D1.5: Project Management Plan (First update) (M18). D1.3 Update which is including a detailed Project Management Plan with a Gantt chart and a Work Breakdown Structure (WBS). It will include a schedule per task, responsible partner related subtasks, related

3.2 WP2: WORK PACKAGE TITLE BASELINE ASSESSMENT AND DEFINITION OF THE PROJECT FRAMEWORK (M1-M24)

The **main objective** of WP2 is to map renewable electricity curtailments and their potential impact on the Energy-Intensive Industries (EIs) sector and its decarbonization process. Moreover, a monitoring and evaluation plan will be developed, based on a set of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) to assess the requirements of CAPTUS conversion technologies. Data gathering, characterization and alignment between industry key actors.

Its **specific objectives** are listed next:

1. Data gathering and mapping of renewable electricity curtailment and their potential impact on EIs.
2. Alignment between key industrial actors for the commercialization of targeted RECs
3. Determination of data requirements to analyse carbon emissions, energy resources and integration with CCU solutions.
4. Identification of Key Performance Indicators.
5. Develop algorithms and models to simulate the best configuration for 3 demo-sites.

WP2 has the following **deliverables** associated:

1. D2.1: CAPTUS REC value chains; opportunities and barriers (M12, RINA-C). Related to Task 2.1, 2.3. Report including the data gathered and information on the main streams involved in the EIs in terms of emissions, materials and energy to identify current bottlenecks and characterise CAPTUS demo-sites.
2. D2.2: Requirements for modelling and simulation (M12, CIRCE). Related to Task 2.2. Specifications and requirements of CAPTUS demo-sites to facilitate the modelling, retrofitting and simulation activities that will improve the performance of the project technologies at the demo-sites. It will also include the necessary specifications to ensure a correct health and safety assessment during the project interventions.
3. D2.3: Evaluation methodology (M15 DRAXIS). Related to Task 2.4. Detailed definition of the identified KPIs considering technical, environmental, economic and social aspects. Guidelines to facilitate KPI monitoring and measuring to follow a common evaluation methodology.
4. D2.4: Requirements for modelling and simulation (final) (M24 CIRCE). Related to Task 2.1, 2.4. Specifications and requirements of CAPTUS demo-sites to facilitate the modelling, retrofitting and simulation activities that will improve the performance of the project technologies at the demo-sites. It will also include the necessary specifications to ensure a correct health and safety assessment during the project interventions.

This is the associated **milestones** for the WP2:

- ❖ MS3: Demo-sites characterized and methodology for KPIs and modelling requirements available (M12) CIRCE.
- ❖ MS4: CAPTUS KPI identified (M15) DRAXIS.
- ❖ MS11: All reports delivered and end of project (M48) CIRCE.

3.3 WP3: PRODUCTION OF ACETATE AND HIGH ENERGY CONTENT TAGS IN THE STEEL INDUSTRY BY A TWO-STEP FERMENTATION PROCESS (M4-M48)

WP3 **main objective** is to develop and demonstrate at TRL7 a complete CCU process by means of an innovative technology based on a multi-stage fermentation process. A gas-substrate fermentation process to convert CO₂-rich steel PSA tail gas into acetic acid will be optimized and demonstrated at ARC steelmaking plant and coupled with a liquid-substrate fermentation process to convert acetic acid (intermediate) into medium and long chain TAGs as final product.

1. Closely looking at its specific objectives:
2. Implementation of a new CO₂ source in the gas fermentation process, together with finetuning at bioreactor scale.
3. Provision of improved yeast strains for TAG production, and bioreactor scale process optimization.
4. Engineering activities for the installation of the (gas) fermentation demo unit at ARC facilities.
5. Upscaling, adaptation and implementation of the solutions for its demonstration under real operating conditions (TRL7).

The following **deliverables** are related to WP3:

- D3.1: Report on strain and process optimization for TAG production at bench scale (M26, CSIC). Related to task 3.2. This deliverable will contain the report on the methodology used for the production and improvement of TAGs by metabolic engineering and systems biology tools. Including lab results using bioreactors (1-5 L).
- D3.2: Report on process optimization and scale-up of fermentative TAG production (M36, BBEPP). Related to task 3.1. Report including fermentation process data (online and offline) performed at bench and pilot scale, as well as gas compositions and yields on each substrate. Determination of productivities/titters, sensitivity to gas contaminants, fermentation parameters, for scale-up and on-site demonstration. DSP process optimized, and process parameters, mass balances and recovery rates for each unit operation determined.
- D3.3: Report on PSA operation optimizations (M32, ARC). Related to task 3.4. Report including data on energy supply fluctuations, optimization of pressure drop levels and switching cycle, gas composition and variations.
- D3.4: Demonstration of TAG production from PSA tail gas (M48, BBEPP). Related to task 3.5. Report on CAPTUS service catalogue lab test and pre-validation results.
- D3.5: Report on process optimization and scale-up of fermentative TAG production (final) (M45, BBEPP). Related to T3.3 Report including fermentation process data (online and offline) performed at bench and pilot scale, as well as gas compositions and yields on each substrate. Determination of productivities/titters, sensitivity to gas contaminants, fermentation parameters, for scale-up and on-site demonstration. DSP process optimized, and process parameters, mass balances and recovery rates for each unit operation determined.

There are four **milestones** related to this WP:

3.4 WP4: PRODUCTION OF BIO-OILS IN THE CHEMICAL INDUSTRY VIA CO₂ ALGAE CULTIVATION FOLLOWED BY HYDROTHERMAL LIQUEFACTION (M4-M48)

The **main objective** of WP4 is to develop and demonstrate at TRL7 a novel technology to convert CO₂ from chemical industry carbon emissions to produce bio-oils as liquid energy carrier. The viability of a demonstration plant in HCH will be designed, optimised and demonstrated by combining two processes: microalgae cultivation using captured and conditioned CO₂, and a hydrothermal liquefaction (HTL) to produce bio-oils from the cultivated algae.

Specific objectives of this work package are as follow:

1. Development of a tailored CO₂ conditioning system to achieve the right conditions for microalgae cultivation.
2. Design and optimisation of specific photobioreactors for cultivation of high energy content microalgae.
3. Development of HTL processes for converting microalgae into valuable bio-oils.
4. Engineering activities for the installation of the targeted CCU technologies in HCH facilities.
5. Upscaling, adaptation and implementation of the solutions for its demonstration under real operating conditions (TRL7).

WP4 presents the following **deliverables**,

- D4.1: Optimization of CCU system in D2 (M22 NOVIS). Related to tasks 4.1, this first deliverable includes the design and engineering of the CO₂ capture/conditioning systems. The assembly and testing of the system at HCH will be also reported.
- D4.2: Microalgae cultivation system (M22, A4F). Related to tasks 4.2, this is the deliverable of the CAPTUS central platform to be tested and enhanced in demonstrations sites.
- D4.3: Optimization of HTL process (M26 CIRCE). This DLV is related to T4.4. Report on the HTL methodology used to produce bio-oils from microalgae, including optimization of the conditions, final properties assessment and main conclusions.
- D4.4: Demonstration of microalgae and bio-oils production (M48 HCH). This DLV is related to T4.4. Report includes the results obtained from the real demonstration of the microalgae cultivation and HTL process, to convert CO₂ into bio- oils (final REC) at HCH facilities.

WP4 has four **milestones** associated:

There are four **milestones** related to this WP:

- ❖ MS5: CCU technol. optimized and ready for operation. Technology conversion systems in process (M22) DRAXIS.
- ❖ MS6: Yeast strains optimization (D1) finalised and HTL system (D2) ready. Electrolyser of D3 ready for operation (M26) CSIC.
- ❖ MS7: On-site integration of the conversion technologies at the EILs facilities and start of the demonstration campaign (M32) ARC.

3.5 WP5: PRODUCTION OF FORMIC ACID IN THE CEMENT INDUSTRY VIA CO₂ ELECTROCHEMICAL REDUCTION (M4-M48)

WP5's **main objective** is to develop and demonstrate at TRL7 a novel technology to convert CO₂ from cement industry emissions into formic acid/formate as liquid energy carrier. The viability of a demonstration plant in CAPTUS will be designed, optimised and demonstrated by combining two processes: the continuous swing adsorption reactor (CSAR) for CO₂ capture and conditioning, and the electrocatalytic reduction of CO₂ (ERCO₂) to formic acid/formate.

As for the **specific objectives**:

1. Optimization of the mobile CSAR CO₂ capture unit and adaptation to the GCPV industrial facilities.
2. Detailed design and engineering of electrochemical conversion technology to produce formic acid as REC.
3. Engineering activities for the scale-up and installation in GCPV facilities.
4. Upscaling, adaptation and implementation of the solutions for its demonstration under real operating conditions (TRL7)

Next, WP5 associated **deliverables** are listed:

- D5.1: Optimization of mobile capture unit and Multiphysics CO₂ electroreduction model (M22 SINTEF). Related to task 5.1. Report on the optimization of the mobile CO₂ capture unit for its proper installation in GCPV facilities. This report will also include the development and validation of the multiphysics CO₂ electroreduction model from SINTEF.
- D5.2: Optimization of ERCO₂ stage and electrolyser design (M22 UNICAN). Related to task 5.2, This report will contain the steps performed for the selection of the optimal cell configuration for an enhanced ERCO₂ step, as well as the construction of the electrochemical reactor prototype. Information of the reactor prototype (25-250 cm²) will be delivered together with the technical viability of the solution performed at lab scale.
- D5.3: Integration and commissioning of CSAR unit and ERCO₂ stage (M32 ARPIA). Related to task 5.4, Detailed description of the design, fabrication and installation of the scaled-up electrochemical reactor with an area >1,000 cm² for the coupling of this CO₂-recycling plant prototype to the photovoltaic solar panels of GCPV.
- D5.4: Demonstration for continuous formic acid production (M48). Related to task 5.5. Results obtained from the real demonstration of the CO₂-recycling plant coupled to the photovoltaic installation, to convert CO₂ into formic acid (final REC) at GCPV facilities.

These are the **milestones** associated with the WP5:

- ❖ MS5: CCU technol. optimized and ready for operation. Technology conversion systems in process (M22) DRAXIS.
- ❖ MS7: On-site integration of the conversion technologies at the EIs facilities and start of the demonstration campaign (M32) ARC.
- ❖ MS11: All reports delivered and end of project (M48) CIRCE.

3.6 WP6 VALIDATION AND IMPACT ASSESSMENT (M33-M48)

The **main objective** of this work package is to analyse in depth the overall sustainability, economic and social viability of the demonstrated concepts for energy intensive industries and evaluate their impact through the whole value chain. It will also include modelling and simulations activities to optimize the CAPTUS technologies to try to maximize the number of economic benefit streams., while the **specific objectives** are detailed next:

1. Quality assessment and upgrading studies of the produced RECs
2. Simulation of the models to analyse the best configuration of the three demo-sites as well as to assess the integration of renewable energy in the processes in the most optimal way
3. To assess the environmental and socio-economic performance of the proposed solutions
4. Evaluation of the economic feasibility of the proposed solutions and identification of the most promising scenario
5. Techno-economic optimisation of different process layouts.

Next, the **deliverables** comprised in work package 6 are detailed bellow:

- D6.1: Quality assessment and upgrading studies (M48 CERTH). This deliverable is related to task 6.1 and contains the studies of the quality assessment of the produced RECs to show their high added value, together with the upgrading studies to demonstrate the adequacy of those in the fabrication of industrial fuels.
- D6.2: Report on use of renewable electricity surplus and avoidance of curtailment losses (M48 CIRCE). Related to task 6.2, 6.3. Reporting on the data on the assets monitored for the energy management system regarding renewable sources integration, consumption patterns and reduction on renewable curtailments.
- D6.3: Report on the results of the LCA, LCC and s-LCA (M48 DRAXIS). This report is also related to Task 6.4. Report on the results of the environmental, economic and social life cycle assessment of the implemented technologies.
- D6.4: Thermo-economic analysis of CAPTUS solutions (M48 UNIGE). Report on the economic viability of CAPTUS solutions including (i) estimation of costs, (ii) impact evaluation, (iii) process profitability, (iv) a pre-feasibility design map, (v) parameters and barriers towards exploitation.

It has two **milestones** associated:

- ❖ MS10: Upgrading studies completed, modelling and techno-economic analysis finalized.
- ❖ MS11: All reports delivered and end of project (M48) CIRCE.

3.7 WP7: EXPLOITATION AND BUSINESS MODELS (M10-M48)

In WP7 partners will work to identify the most suitable strategies and market mechanisms for market-uptake of RECs production in industrial processes. This will help construct the most suitable business use cases to increase decarbonisation in industrial processes. Also, this WP will analyse the Key Exploitable Results (KERs), focusing on the IPR management among partners. Finally, an analysis of challenges for the replication of solutions is also expected.

Specific objectives of this work package are:

1. To provide a list of best practices for the processes up-scaling and develop guidelines to enhance the performance of the conversion processes in CAPTUS demo-sites
2. To consolidate the most suitable strategy for the exploitation of the project's results, focusing on the IPR management among partners and the regulatory and market readiness towards TRL9 after the project's completion
3. To develop learning resources and building programmes supporting the understanding and use of the project outcomes
4. To develop a complete roadmap for the commercialisation of CAPTUS technologies and processes and identify opportunities for CAPTUS Key Exploitable Results.
5. To identify legal, social and financial gaps and provide recommendations to overcome those gaps

Deliverables corresponding to work package 7 are listed below,

- D7.1: Replication of CAPTUS solutions in EII sectors and market analysis (M36, EEIPP). Related to task 7.5. Report on the identified legal, social and financial barriers and proposed solutions to overcome them and promote the replication of CAPTUS solutions. It will also include a report on the three additional replicators results and catalogue identifying new regions with great potential for CAPTUS expansion based on the project outcomes.
- D7.2: Exploitation strategy and IPR management (first version) (M12, GF). Task related are 7.2. Document including the definition of the exploitation strategy and pathways, IPR review and management and final IPR manual including agreements among the partners.
- D7.3: Best practices and business models (M36 RINA-C). This deliverable is related to task 7.4 and is a review of the best practices and promising innovative business models for CAPTUS solutions.
- D7.4: Exploitation strategy and IPR management (second version) (M24, FE). Task related are 7.2. D7.2 updated. Document including the definition of the exploitation strategy and pathways, IPR review and management and final IPR manual including agreements among the partners.
- D7.5: Replication of CAPTUS solutions in EII sectors and market analysis (final) (M48 EEIPP). This deliverable is related to task 7.5 and 7.3. D7.1 updated. Report on the identified legal, social and financial barriers and proposed solutions to overcome them and promote the replication of CAPTUS solutions. It will also include a report on the three additional replicators results and catalogue identifying new regions with great potential for CAPTUS expansion based on the project outcomes.
- D7.4: Exploitation strategy and IPR management (second version) (M48, FE). Task related are 7.2. D7.4 Document including the definition of the exploitation strategy and pathways,

3.8 WP8 : DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION (M1-M48)

The **Main objective** of this work package is to define and implement dissemination and communication activities with extensive audience to be carried out throughout (and after) the project to ensure that CAPTUS results will effectively benefit the European energy sector and reach the market.

As for its **specific objectives**:

1. To define a dissemination and communication strategy
2. To identify needs and prepare materials for the promotion and communication of the project
3. To monitor the execution of the C&D activities with a continuous penetration in the main target groups
4. To identify and take advantage of synergies with other initiatives and funding opportunities.

WP8 **deliverables** are listed next:

- D8.1: Communication & dissemination plan (first version) (M6 SIG). Related to task 8.1.
 - 1) Identification of CAPTUS stakeholders/profiling; 2) Dissemination and communication methods, channels, associated activities and tools to reach the expected impacts; 3) Dissemination and communication procedures; 4) Schedule and complementarities among partners. 5) Initial exploitation strategy.
- D8.2: Project website and communication materials (M6). Related to task 8.2. Description and publication of project logo, website, brochure, roll-up, poster and other communication materials prepared to date, as well as schedule for other communication actions and materials.
- D8.3: Synergies with other projects and engagement actions (M48 SIG). Related to task 8.5. Summary of actions and results related to the collaboration and synergies with other innovation projects and platforms.
- D8.4: Communication & dissemination plan (second version) (M18 SIG). Related to task 8.1. D8.1 updated, 1) Identification of CAPTUS stakeholders/profiling; 2) Dissemination and communication methods, channels, associated activities and tools to reach the expected impacts; 3) Dissemination and communication procedures; 4) Schedule and complementarities among partners. 5) Initial exploitation strategy.
- D8.5: Communication & dissemination plan (third version) (M36 SIG). Related to task 8.1. D8.4 updated, 1) Identification of CAPTUS stakeholders/profiling; 2) Dissemination and communication methods, channels, associated activities and tools to reach the expected impacts; 3) Dissemination and communication procedures; 4) Schedule and complementarities among partners. 5) Initial exploitation strategy.
- D8.6: Communication & dissemination plan (second version) (M18 SIG). Related to task 8.1. D8.5 updated, 1) Identification of CAPTUS stakeholders/profiling; 2) Dissemination and communication methods, channels, associated activities and tools to reach the expected impacts; 3) Dissemination and communication procedures; 4) Schedule and complementarities among partners. 5) Initial exploitation strategy.

4 WORK PACKAGES INTERACTION

All activities encompassed within the scope of the project shall receive steadfast support through a cohesive and streamlined management and coordination structure operating under the purview of Work Package 1 (WP1). The primary objective of WP1 is to cultivate an efficient and all-encompassing administrative, financial, technical, and legal management framework to guarantee the successful execution of the project.

WP2 is primarily dedicated to the meticulous characterization of data, barriers, resources, and requirements, all of which will serve as the foundational reference for the development of CAPTUS solutions within the more technically oriented work packages. Notably, in WP2, key performance indicators (KPIs) have been established, which shall be subject to monitoring both prior to and subsequent to the implementation of the technologies. These defined KPIs are instrumental in setting realistic and achievable objectives, vital to the triumphant implementation of the demo-site.

The concurrent development and demonstration of CAPTUS technologies are executed in WP3, WP4, and WP5, each allocated to one of the three selected demo-sites. The advancement of these three work packages shall adhere to a parallel structure: initially, encompassing the essential phases of design, development, and optimization of the Capture, Utilization, and Utilization (CUU) and conversion technologies; subsequently, the refined systems will undergo engineering, scaling-up, and integration into the respective industrial facilities; ultimately culminating in the actual demonstration of CAPTUS solutions, attaining the necessary Technology Readiness Level (TRL) 7.

Within WP6, a comprehensive array of impact assessments will be conducted, encompassing social, technical, and cost-benefit analyses. These assessments will play a pivotal role in establishing the feasibility and cost-efficiency of the proposed solutions. Additionally, this Work Package will undertake quality evaluations and upgrading studies of the obtained liquid Renewable Energy Carriers (RECs) to verify their suitability for end use in the energy sector.

Furthermore, an in-depth examination and optimization of the integration of available renewable sources will be a key focus of WP6. The primary objective here is to mitigate the curtailment of renewable electricity while enhancing the overall efficiency and viability of renewable electricity systems. This integration will work in tandem with efforts to curtail carbon emissions, furthering the synergy between sustainable energy practices and climate change mitigation.

In WP7, the conclusions drawn from the demonstration activities will be leveraged to formulate comprehensive exploitation and replication strategies. These strategies will outline how the CAPTUS solutions can be effectively utilized and expanded beyond the initial demo-sites. Additionally, an evaluation of the regulatory and standardisation landscape will be conducted to identify any pertinent requirements or guidelines that need to be adhered to for widespread adoption.

Moreover, WP7 will play a pivotal role in contributing to the creation of a conducive framework that fosters the uptake of CAPTUS solutions within the context of profitable business models. By identifying and addressing potential barriers and challenges, this work package aims to facilitate the successful integration of CAPTUS technologies into the market, promoting their viability and scalability for sustainable commercial ventures.

Concurrent with the methodology phases, WP8 will encompass communication and dissemination activities, actively undertaken by all project partners with the objective of engaging the widest possible audience. These activities will be focused on effectively communicating the progress,

findings, and outcomes of the project to various stakeholders, including the scientific community, industry experts, policymakers, and the general public.

Through strategic communication efforts, such as workshops, conferences, publications, online platforms, and outreach events, the partners will seek to raise awareness about the project's objectives, methodologies, and results. By fostering active engagement and knowledge-sharing, WP8 aims to maximize the impact of the CAPTUS project, promoting its significance and potential contributions to the broader community.

Figure 19: CAPTUS PERT Chart.

5 RISK ASSESSMENT

Below is a preliminary table of potential risks that may arise during the implementation of CAPTUS, along with their corresponding contingency plans. Please note that this section will be subject to updates throughout the project execution to include any newly identified or unforeseen risks.

Table 2: CAPTUS Critical risks & risk management strategy

RISK NUMBER	DESCRIPTION	WORK PACKAGE NO(S)	PROPOSED MITIGATION MEASURES
1	Closing the activity of one company or partner leaving the consortium	WP1	The consortium is highly qualified and would assume tasks from a partner leaving the project. Otherwise, they would find within their large contact network the best partner for assuming the role lost.
2	Poor communication flow between partners	WP1	An open and dialectic approach will be applied in all the consortium meetings and correspondence and communication will be promoted and ensured by the PC.
3	Lack of financial resources	WP1	Solvency of project partners has been assessed, ensuring their financial resources during the project execution. Most partners have already participated in national or EU projects, having wide experience and history, which reduces this risk.
4	Error in the estimation of the tasks' duration	WP1	Steering of the project will be frequent. Milestones and deliverables have been placed for control. Under delays detection PC will encourage a review of task procedure and partners to place extra effort.
5	Delay in the development of CAPTUS R&I innovations and solutions	WP1	Efforts allocated, and Gantt diagram have been designed avoiding possible delays in the deliveries. If some delay occurred, the task/WP leader will engage all necessary efforts to deliver the solution as soon as possible. Also, the necessary capabilities are involved in the consortium so that no big delays occur.
6	Problems between partners (disagreements etc.)	WP1	The project handbook (D1.1) will include all the procedures already accepted in the CA. A democratic and dialectic approach will be applied in all the consortium meetings and correspondence. IPR issues will be discussed

			and established within a common CA, signed by all the partners.
7	Quality, scope and delay of partners work	WP1	A compulsory work plan is established with operative plan to be prepared by WP leaders to avoid low quality, loss of direction or too overload actions. In case this is detected, PC will enter in contact with WP leader to revise. Key DLV will always go through a review process including CIRCE and TPs.
8	Decrease of the availability of key components in the market if the conflict with Ukraine is exacerbating	WP3, WP4, WP5	When possible, substitute materials will be used in an attempt to cut costs. If this is not possible, project partners will undertake additional costs for the sake of the project.
9	Difficulties to obtain valuable information from DSO companies regarding grid curtailment in the area of the demo-sites	WP3, WP4, WP5	Collaboration with DSO will be promoted by synergies with ongoing project working on grid flexibility and sharing CAPTUS key outcomes regarding the management and integration electricity surplus.
10	Unexpectedly low productivities by <i>Y. lipolytica</i> on tail gas-derived acetic acid or inefficient DSP led to insufficient quantities of target TAGs in D1	WP3	Optimize process at bench scale, along with additional strain optimization. Use available BBEP fermenters up to 15 m ³ scale to produce sufficient fermentation broth for TAG recovery with mock feed. Optimize bottleneck DSP unit operation. Test other DSP techniques (chemical cell disruption using green organic solvents, extraction and solvent recuperation) or their combinations.
11	Impurities of the flue gas affecting the washing process in D2	WP4	This can be overcome, by adding a second washing column and including a fine filter in the washing columns, to make the water reusable.
12	Effect of effluent	WP5	Design of a technical pre-treatment (e.g., activated carbon filter) that can remove the

	impurities (from GCPV) on the CO ₂ capture process in D3		impurities generated by GCPV in the cement industry to improve the durability and operability of the CSAR. Another option will be sorbent replenishment, but the choice will depend on cost impacts.
13	Difficulties with electrolyser prototype operation under industrial conditions	WP5	Revision of the electrolyser design and the range of operating conditions. Besides, the performance of the process will be studied by computational fluid dynamics (CFD) to perform the calculations required to simulate the streams
14	Difficulties during the scale-up of ERCO2 pilot and proper connection to the CO ₂ capture plant in D3	WP5	Re-engineering of the designed prototype for CO ₂ capture and electrochemical conversion towards formic acid and formate, by employing filter press reactors with a geometric area of 250 cm ² , which have been previously optimized, in a parallel configuration.
15	Stoppage of production in one of the CAPTUS industries due to an excessive increase in energy costs	WP5	At the beginning of CAPTUS, gas samples from EIs will be collected and, in case the production stops due to an excessive increment in the energy cost, these samples will be employed for the conversion processes.
16	Difficulties in the integration of the renewable energy in the demo-sites	WP3, WP4, WP5	In case that the renewable energy resources cannot supply the required inputs, the CAPTUS solutions will be connected to alternatives energy sources like provisional ESS or PV solar panels.
17	Ineffective exploitation strategy and/or business models	WP7	CAPTUS counts with industrial and research partners with experience in developing, implementing and managing similar solutions, as well as business experts like RINA-C with a large portfolio of clients and covering the entire value creation chain, which ensures enough expertise to modify and adapt the exploitation strategy in case it is required.
18	Poor dissemination to the stakeholders	WP8	Potential stakeholders, previously European financed projects as well as a preliminary dissemination and awareness plan, specifying target audiences (who) and the best

			communication channels (how), have been identified and detailed. Market audience is also identified at proposal stage.
19	Weak internal communication	WP8	Weak communication among partners makes difficult to disseminate and promote the project developments. CIRCE will set up bi-monthly teleconferences with the WP leaders to strengthen internal communication and to ensure the flow of information.

6 CONCLUSION

This report addresses the main objectives of the CAPTUS project. While the CAPTUS objectives are well documented in the action document, the details are defined in this report, summarizing the contributions of all partners.

In this document, the objectives of the work packages and their interdependencies have been identified and defined. The main findings and results of the tasks are presented in this report, consolidating them within a well-organized structure. All participants in the project have defined their roles and responsibilities in the different work packages, as well as their main areas of expertise.

The objectives of the CAPTUS work packages are clearly defined, and the checkpoints for monitoring work progress are determined, along with the breakdown of the different tasks and subtasks that will be undertaken within the various work packages. Finally, all possible interactions and conflicts are constructed based on the information received from the work package participants.

Therefore, this deliverable constitutes a comprehensive guide to the CAPTUS project, aiming to minimize misunderstandings, conflicts, and resource waste. Each partner or team will further develop their methods or strategies using this document as a baseline.